

Tribal agency and the translocalization of the Middle East: the European mandates, the Arab Bedouins and the making of the post-Ottoman order*

M. Talha Çiçek

University College Dublin, Ireland

m.cicek@ucd.ie

ABSTRACT

This article argues that the agency of the Arab Bedouin across state borders played a remarkable role in the establishment of a translocal order containing Syria, Iraq, Saudi Arabia and Jordan. It first examines the translocalization of tribal nationality highlighting their achievements to remain in a trans-border existence against French and British mandates, and, second, reveals the constructive roles played by tribes in the establishment of a tranquil translocal order by preventing illicit arms trade. Third, it indicates their efforts in the ‘cross-spatialization’ of the national fields. Finally, it uncovers the tribal struggle against Wahhabi expansionism, which threatened a regionwide translocal formation.

This article argues that the translocal agency of the Arab Bedouin across state borders played a significant role in the emergence of the post-Ottoman Middle East in the first decades of the mandate rules. Their actions, reactions and attitudes on a crucial number of occasions reshaped government policies and had a significant impact in the emergence of a translocal regional order. In this regard, this article first focuses on the issue of tribal nationality in Syria and Iraq and examines their efforts to remain in a trans-border existence against the British and French, who sought to restrict their movements within national boundaries. Second, it reveals the tribal struggle against Wahhabi expansionism, which threatened the translocal existence of the Bedouin groups. Third, it indicates the constructive role played by various tribal leaders in the establishment of a tranquil regional order by preventing illicit arms trade, by which they became the partners of states, translocalizing their political projects envisioned nationally in Syria, Iraq, Jordan and Arabia. Finally, it unearths the tribal agency in the making of political borders and highlights the cross-border exemptions made to the tribal communities. This article draws on the French and British archival sources, Arabic newspapers, and other primary sources in various languages.

On 20 July 1923 a conference for the demarcation of the Iraq-Syria border opened in Deir al-Zor, Syria, a *mutasarrifate* established in the 1860s by the Ottomans at the crossroads of the grazing lands of

* I would like to acknowledge that this chapter is based on research conducted within the framework of CAPITALEAST: Global Capitalism and Rurality: Agency, Commodification and Socio-Ecological Transformation of the Middle Eastern Countryside, 1870–1945, a project generously supported by a Consolidator Grant from the European Research Council (Grant Agreement Number: 101124215).

various Syrian and Iraqi tribes around the Euphrates basin. The Anglo-Iraqi delegation – which included the most prominent Iraqi tribal leaders such as Fahd Bey ibn Hadhdhāl of the Amārāt, Ali Sulaimān of the Dulaim, Rajā al-Sattām of the Jaraifā as well as British and Iraqi officials – was received at the border by a well-armed French military convoy. ‘Ajil al-Yāwir, the sheikh of the Shammār tribe in Iraq, preferred to come in his own car. The French mandate officials took tight security measures to prevent any attack on the convoy, as it contained the Iraqi tribal sheikhs, who had long-lasting disputes and a history of bloodshed with the Syrian tribes. In addition to the French and Syrian officials, the Syrian participants of the conference comprised of the sheikhs of the Aqaidāt, Bū-Sarāyā, Baggāra and Sabkha tribes. A salon in the Deir al-Zor government house *sérail* was reserved for the conference and the municipal police provided security. Ultimately considered as a precondition of a functioning border, many disputes between the Iraqi and Syrian tribes were discussed until 26 July 1923, and many of the tribal conflicts were concluded, at least with an armistice through bilateral negotiations between the Iraqi and Syrian tribes. Tribal customs and traditions were largely observed in addressing the disputes.¹

Such a conference was considered necessary after several failed attempts to delimit the Syrian-Iraqi border by the mandatory states, which eventually understood the cruciality of recognizing the tribal trans-border agency for a sustainable regional order in the Middle East. The French and British empires had to accept the mobile character of the tribal groups and develop interstate mechanisms that resulted in the maintenance of the tribal lifestyle in a translocal/trans-border manner, as in the Ottoman times. This experience was almost identical to the Ottoman experience with the tribes in the mid nineteenth century, when long-lasting hostilities took place between the empire and the Arab Bedouin as the empire officials wanted to restrict their mobility and transform their lifestyles. The Ottoman government eventually had to reconcile with the tribal communities in the early 1870s on the principle of the immunity of their pastures and migrant lifestyle, and accepting tribal authority in the desert and abandon projects aimed at the transformation of the desert space.²

The tribal groups such as the Fid’an, al-Jarbā, Amārāt, Ruwalla, Wuld Alī and Seb’a who seasonally migrated between Syria, Jordan, Iraq and Saudi Arabia were among the most influential political and social groups in the region who controlled enormous pasture lands in the Syrian and Iraqi countryside since the late eighteenth century and were tied in networks of real or fictive kinship that provided (and still provide) its members with solidarity and cohesiveness. According to one scholar, ‘Until the 1920s about two-thirds of what was to become the Syrian Republic was controlled by Bedouin, with the camel herders of the ‘Anaza confederation as a hegemonic force among them.’³ In spite of regional differentiations from Syria and Iraq to Jordan and Saudi Arabia – and considerable transformations in their social structure during the twentieth century – they still maintain a ‘corporatist lifestyle’ in the rural areas of these countries based on the kinship solidarity, which granted them considerable social, spatial and economic agency.⁴ Therefore, situating them in the Middle East politics with a historical perspective as active ‘policy-makers’ rather than ‘silent subjects’ fills an important gap in the history of the region.

Many studies have examined the transformation of nomadic society and culture, and the desert policies of successive Middle Eastern regimes. In recent years, groundbreaking monographs have been published unearthing the agency of the tribal groups and their roles in the making of the modern Middle East during the Ottoman era. This research successfully synthesized the political, economic, social and environmental historical perspectives.⁵ For the post-Ottoman era, however, the great majority of historical studies on the

¹ Centre des Archives diplomatiques de Nantes (hereafter C.A.D.N.), ISL/1/V/558, ‘Rapport du Colonel Andrea, président de la délégation syrienne a la Conférence de Deir-ez-Zor’, Deir al-Zor, 30 July 1923.

² For details, see M. T. Çiçek, *Negotiating Empire in the Middle East: Ottomans and Arab Nomads in the Modern Era, 1840–1914* (Cambridge, 2021).

³ J. Büssow, ‘Bedouin historiography in the making: an indigenous history of the Hasana tribe in Syria’, in *Nomadism in der ‘Alten Welt’*, ed. L. Prager (Münster, 2012), pp. 160–83, at p. 163.

⁴ For a wonderful examination of ‘corporatism’, see J. Büssow und A. Meier, ‘Ottoman corporatism, eighteenth to twentieth centuries: beyond the state-society paradigm in Middle Eastern history’, in *Ways of Knowing Muslim Cultures and Societies*, ed. S. Amir-Moazami, B. Gräf and B. Krawietz (Boston, Mass., 2019), pp. 81–110; see also H. Dukhan, ‘Tribes and tribalism in the Syrian uprising’, *Tribes & Neighbourhoods*, vi (2014), 1–28.

⁵ See, e.g., N. Barakat, *Bedouin Bureaucrats: Mobility and Property in the Ottoman Empire* (Stanford, 2023); S. Dolbee, *Locusts of Power: Borders, Empire and Environment in the Modern Middle East* (Cambridge, 2023); Çiçek, *Negotiating Empire*; F. H. Husain, *Rivers of the Sultan: the Tigris and Euphrates in the Ottoman Empire* (Oxford, 2021); and Z. Pehlivan, *The Political Ecology of Violence: Peasants and Pastoralists in the Last Ottoman Century* (Cambridge, 2024).

tribal past has (until recently) dealt with government policies towards nomads by focusing on the subjects such as settlement projects, state expansionism and coercive attempts to dissociate migrant societies. In this regard, the volumes edited by Philip S. Khoury and Joseph Kostiner, Martha Mundy and Basim Musallam, and Eugene Rogan and Tariq Tell add remarkably to our knowledge.⁶ Although they have illuminated plenty of issues regarding state-nomad relations in the Middle East, and made very important contributions to the growing literature on the Bedouin, the great majority of the chapters, implicitly or explicitly, either adopt a state-centric approach and treat the tribes as passive objects of government policies, or examine the various aspects of tribal life in the desert. Other scholars have specifically analysed the British, French and Saudi policies of tribal communities in the interwar period.⁷ In general, they have focused on the ‘pacification’, ‘co-operation’ and ‘incorporation’ policies adopted by the mandates and the Saudi kingdom for the desert. According to such perspectives, it was the states who ‘decided’ and who ‘abandoned’ rather than the nomads who ‘reacted’ and ‘rejected’ the government plans and compelled the governments to act in a way that the tribespeople would accept. Therefore, it is difficult to distinguish the tribal agency in the existing literature, which was usually inclined to analyse the government policies to colonize the desert and transform the nomadic lifestyle. Such approaches consequently muted tribal voices and ignored their agency during the period when the contemporary Middle East emerged.

However, a number of more nuanced studies have been published that counterbalance the dominance of the above research by pointing to the complexity of the Middle East’s social and political matrix and highlighting the agency of the tribal communities on various occasions. In a brilliant article, Büssow demonstrates how lower ranking tribal representatives entered into direct negotiations with other Bedouin leaders and government representatives by examining Seb’a-’Abada Bedouin, a subgroup of the ‘Anaza, in the Syrian mandate.⁸ In a recent study, Philippe Pétriat indicates the pivotal role of the Arab nomads and their camels in the regional trade of the Middle East.⁹ Examining the long tradition of ‘Ottoman corporatism’ with a *longue durée* perspective, Meier and Büssow highlight realms of Ottoman society that went beyond the control of the state.¹⁰

This article builds on the lines of investigation opened by these studies and, therefore, argues that tribal mobility across state borders and the ability to play one state against the other made the tribes important regional actors whose reactions and attitudes, on a crucial number of occasions, reshaped government policies, and had a remarkable impact on the emergence of the new regional order. In this regard, it puts the tribal agency under scrutiny and defines it as the combination of leadership activities and strong social solidarity that consolidated the tribal leadership in the local and regional politics. These two components frequently act in harmony and constitute the tribal agency. It was not easy for a tribal sheikh to disregard the interests and concerns of his fellow tribespeople, which would lead to great crises within the tribes.¹¹ The sheikhs persuaded their own community to act in line with them when the governments’ demands and their fellow tribespeople’s interests conflicted and they had to accept these demands. Thus, there was a process of consent production within tribes.

*

Tribal affiliations were not replaced by individual citizenship of the emerging national states during the mandate era. The insistence of tribes on maintaining group solidarity and the inadequate technologies

⁶ P. S. Khoury and J. Kostiner, *Tribes and State Formation in the Middle East* (Berkeley, Calif., 1990); *The Transformation of Nomadic Society in the Arab East*, ed. M. Mundy and B. Musallam (Cambridge, 2000); and E. Rogan and T. Tell, *Village, Steppe and State: the Social Origins of Modern Jordan* (London, 1994).

⁷ R. S. G. Fletcher, *British Imperialism and ‘the Tribal Question’* (Oxford, 2015); for the French policies in Syria, see D. Neep, *Occupying Syria Under French Mandate* (Cambridge, 2012); and J. Kostiner, ‘Transforming dualities: tribe and state formation in Saudi Arabia’, in Khoury and Kostiner, *Tribes and State Formation*, pp. 226–52.

⁸ J. Büssow, ‘Negotiating the future of a Bedouin polity in mandatory Syria: political dynamics of the Sba’a-’Abada during the 1930s’, *Nomadic Peoples*, xv (2011), 70–95. For a similar study, see L. Stocker, ‘The “camel dispute”: cross-border mobility and tribal conflicts in the Iraqi-Syrian borderland, 1929–34’, in *Regimes of Mobility: Borders and State Formation in the Middle East, 1918–1946*, ed. J. Tejel and R. H. Öztan (Edinburgh, 2022), pp. 319–50.

⁹ P. Pétriat, *The Last Caravan: Camels, Traders and the Markets in the Middle East* (Cambridge, 2025); and P. Pétriat, ‘The uneven age of speed: caravans, technology, and mobility in the late Ottoman and post-Ottoman Middle East’, *International Journal of Middle East Studies*, liii (2021), 273–90.

¹⁰ Büssow and Meier, ‘Ottoman corporatism’.

¹¹ For an example, see Büssow, ‘Future of a Bedouin polity’.

of control available to states were among the factors that prevented this transformation, despite the increase in airpower and automobiles.¹² As the establishment of the proper authority of a state would result in a reduction of certain privileges and sacrificing freedom of trans-border movement, tribes resisted 'nationalization' and bargained for their own terms to be affiliated to the mandatory states. The difficulty of individualizing citizenship in inaccessible desert areas made their collective subordination to a state the 'inevitable optional'. Because it would minimize the state's control over Bedouin communities, this formula was also attractive for the tribes. This consequently reinforced tribal hierarchies that increased the agency of tribes in Middle Eastern politics and maintained tribal culture as the dominant paradigm determining the order of things in rural areas. Therefore, the 'nationalization' of the tribal communities can rather be defined as a 'collective contract' than a 'social contract' of citizenship, for which the mandates, King Faisal, Amir Abdullah and Ibn Saud struggled.¹³

The intertwining between the official recognition of a sheikh by a state and the issue of his fellow tribesmen's nationality caused long-lasting struggles among tribal sheikhs to be officially appointed to paramount sheikhship in the most advantageous area for themselves and their tribes. Since the Ottoman times, the official recognition of a sheikh for a particular region greatly increased the sheikh's prestige in tribal society, as the sheikh and his followers acquired the rights to use markets and pastures there. It also expanded the tribal power in the desert, as other tribes' use of the pastures and the bazaars in this particular region were subject to the permission of the officially recognized sheikh. Therefore, tribal sheikhs vehemently struggled with each other to get this official title in the Ottoman era and its aftermath, which occasionally led to the division of the Shammār and 'Anaza tribes and brought about their migration from one area to another.

In this regard, Dahhām al-Hādī's struggle with the British for Mosul is a highly representative example as it demonstrates how the issue of the Shammār's nationality was transformed into a process of negotiation that the sheikh played between King Faisal and the British and French empires. In fact, tribal actors like al-Hādī used their nationality and the services they would provide in return as a bargaining chip between the surrounding states to maintain their trans-border mobile existence.¹⁴ In follow-up to the Ottoman practice of appointing a separate sheikh to the Mosuli Shammārs,¹⁵ al-Hādī had been recognized by the British as the paramount sheikh of the Shammār in Mosul in place of his grandfather al-Āsī after the occupation of Iraq. However, his relations with the Turks¹⁶ and his support for the 1920 Iraq Revolt (Thawrat 'Ishriyn) led the British to replace him with his first cousin 'Ajīl al-Yāwīr.¹⁷ A Shammār sheikh who had good relations with the Kemalists was considered by the British a potential threat for their rule in Mosul as Turkey did not abandon their sovereignty rights to the region until 1926.¹⁸ The French, in the meantime, needed a strong man as the leader of the Syrian Shammārs to fill the power vacuum in the Jazīra region and hence appointed al-Hādī as the paramount sheikh of the Syrian Shammārs immediately after the beginning of the mandate. Al-Hādī's main concern, however, was to preserve his strong influence among both the Iraqi and Syrian Shammārs and to maintain his popularity and power in both countries as a translocal actor, which he by and large achieved at least during the 1920s.¹⁹

¹² Indeed, air power ended up being an unintended catalyst for tribal agency, as neither the R.A.F.'s planes nor the technology of the armoured car could operate without the intelligence provided by tribal informants on the ground. This reinforced tribal agency by creating a relationship of dependency between certain tribal groups/leaders and the mandatory states. For some details, see J. B. Glubb, *War in the Desert* (London, 1960), pp. 155–75; and Neep, *Occupying Syria*, ch 7.

¹³ The Iraqi government, for instance, promised tax exemptions and watering and grazing areas for the tribal animals to persuade them to change nationality, which would expand its physical boundary and political influence into Syria (C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/552, 'Exposé de la situation de tribus nomades en 1930', Beirut, 6 Jan. 1930).

¹⁴ The National Archives of the U.K., CO 730/20, 'Intelligence report', Baghdad, 1 March 1922; for a recent study on al-Hādī's situation during the mandate era, see: L. Stocker, "Bordering" the Shammar Jarbā: The Case of the Shaykh Dahhām al-Hādī in the Post-Ottoman Jazīra, *Die Welt des Islams* (published online ahead of print 2025).

For the Ottoman era policies, see Çiçek, *Negotiating Empire*, ch 5; and Dolbee, *Locusts of Power*, ch. 2.

¹⁶ Max Freiherr von Oppenheim, *Die Bedouinen*, i: *Die Bedouinenstämme in Mesopotamien und Syrien* (Wiesbaden, 1952), p. 142.

¹⁷ H. M. S. Hadhr, *Al-Tārikh al-Siyāsī li Āl-i Muhammad al-Jarbā wa Shammār fi Najd wa Arz al-Jazīra 1500–1921* (Mosul, 2013), pp. 16, 312.

¹⁸ For details on the Kemalist policies regarding Mosul and the Jazīra region, see M. Budak, *İdealden Gerçeğe* (Istanbul, 2002), pp. 167–74, 336–49.

¹⁹ T.N.A., CO 730/2, Baghdad, 15 June 1921.

To that end, following an amnesty by the British for the supporters of the 1920 Revolt,²⁰ al-Hādī travelled to Mosul in June 1921, intending to reconcile with the British to secure his position in Iraq.²¹ As his grandfather al-Āsī was the sheikh of the Shammār tribes in Mosul during the 1890s and he was originally an Iraqi sheikh, it was more lucrative for him to be the paramount sheikh of the Iraqi Shammārs and an Iraqi citizen.²² To conclude a naturalization contract, al-Hādī stayed in Mosul for a month, where he finally signed an agreement, limited to allowing him and his followers to visit Mosul without prior permission, but did not resolve the issue of nationality.²³ Shortly afterwards, probably as a manoeuvre to obtain Iraqi nationality and be appointed to the paramount sheikhship, al-Hādī declared his allegiance to King Faisal.²⁴ However, both the British and the king clearly preferred his cousin al-Yāwīr, which compelled al-Hādī to settle for a number of market and pasture privileges in Mosul that were actually for the paramount sheikhs. In this way, he enjoyed extensive rights in Iraq, where he was not a citizen, and maintained the transnational character of his community.

Assuming this recognition to be the first stage, al-Hādī maintained his campaign for the paramount sheikhship of the Iraqi Shammārs. However, when al-Yāwīr was reappointed to the post in April 1922, al-Hādī protested the appointment decision before the government and occasionally kept the strategic Deir al-Zor Road closed to traffic by attacking convoys of motor vehicles and causing other security problems to express his anger to the decision. In this way, the sheikh tried to undermine the confidence of the British and King Faisal²⁵ in al-Yāwīr's leadership capacity, as this had been a frequent method of power display since Ottoman times to be promoted to official sheikhship.²⁶ His actions were so threatening to the regional order that one of the attacks his tribespeople carried out on the Mosuli merchant Abdullah Hasso continued to cause problems between the French and British mandates even in 1926.²⁷ Finally, in August 1922 al-Hādī was invited to Baghdad and given the status of an official sheikhship, similar to his status in Syria. Nevertheless, it was an important acquisition for him to enter Mosul's markets without al-Yāwīr's permission and approval.²⁸

While al-Hādī was trying to protect his position in Mosul, a less salaried but still attractive position (the paramount sheikhship of the Syrian Shammārs) awaited him in Syria.²⁹ In addition, the sheikh was planning to expand his influence on the Raqqa region of Syria against the Fid'an of the 'Anaza.³⁰ For the French, they had recognized Mish'al al-Fāris as the sheikh of all the Syrian Shammārs,³¹ but were apparently dissatisfied with his performance, which compelled them to contact al-Hādī once again.³² According to a report from April 1923, al-Hādī held numerous meetings with the French to discuss the issue of the sheikhship of the Syrian Shammār,³³ and was soon appointed by them for this post. The French also wanted to annex the Jabal Sinjar region of Iraq to the Syrian Mandate³⁴ and thereby strengthen its position in Mosul, for which al-Hādī was an ideal partner.³⁵ Therefore, his high popularity among the Shammār tribes in Mosul significantly contributed to the improvement of his relations with the French authorities. In July 1923 he travelled to Aleppo to visit the French High Commissioner for Syria and expressed that the meeting was satisfactory.³⁶

²⁰ Hadhr, *Al-Tārīkh al-Siyāsī*, p. 431.

²¹ T.N.A., CO 730/3, Baghdad, 1 June 1921.

²² For an analysis on this, see C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/562, Dobb to high commissioner, 31 March 1928.

²³ T.N.A., CO 730/4, Baghdad, 1 Aug. 1921.

²⁴ T.N.A., CO 730/5, Baghdad, 1 Sept. 1921.

²⁵ Ajil al-Yāwīr developed relations with the Arab nationalist societies, which presumably made him preferable for the king (Hadhr, *Al-Tārīkh al-Siyāsī*, p. 321).

²⁶ T.N.A., CO 730/22, 'Intelligence report', Baghdad, 15 May 1922.

²⁷ C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/562, High commissioner to Henry de Jouvenel, Baghdad, 10 March 1926.

²⁸ T.N.A., CO 730/23, 'Intelligence report', Baghdad, 1 Aug. 1922.

²⁹ For a comparison of the salaries, see P. Khoury, 'The tribal shaykh, French tribal policy, and the nationalist movement in Syria between two world wars', *Middle Eastern Studies*, xviii (1982), 180–93.

³⁰ M. A. al-Hāmid al-Hamīd, *Ashā'ir al-Raqqā wa al-Jazīra: Al-Tārīkh wa al-Mawrūth* (Al-Raqqā, 2003), p. 186.

³¹ T.N.A., CO 730/23, 'Intelligence report', Baghdad, 1 Aug. 1922.

³² The later French reports indicate that they were not happy with Dāhhām's irreconcilable character. For instance, his attack on Mish'al al-Fāris in alliance with the Jabbur and Tay tribes caused their resentment (see C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/562, Cabinet politique, 'L'affaire d'El-Bidea', Deir al-Zor, 27 Apr. 1926), but they presumably invested him to keep his tribe under control and benefit from his authority to pacify the Shammār.

³³ T.N.A., CO 730/39, 'Intelligence report', Baghdad, 1 Apr. 1923.

³⁴ For some details on the Franco-British rivalry in the Jazīra region and Mosul, see J. Barr, *A Line in the Sand: Britain, France and the Struggle That Shaped the Middle East* (London, 2011), pp. 64–78, 104–16.

³⁵ T.N.A., CO 730/39, 'Intelligence report', Baghdad, 15 Apr. 1923.

³⁶ T.N.A., CO 730/41, 'Intelligence report', Baghdad, 26 July 1923.

Having improved the relations with the French, and thus being confident about their status, al-Hādī and his followers began to cross the border and attack Iraqi caravans. Their intention was to improve their status in Iraq as much as possible by forcing British authorities to negotiate them for the security of the Iraqi rural areas in the north. To that end, a caravan belonging to a wealthy merchant of Mosul was completely robbed. Almost all car drivers using the trans-desert routes complained that al-Hādī's men demanded five Turkish liras of them during their desert journeys.³⁷ In September 1923 alone three attacks on Iraqi travellers by al-Hādī's people were reported, which did not cease in subsequent years.³⁸

Al-Hādī maintained his attacks against the Iraqi tribes and undermined the regional security until late 1920s, which caused serious crises between the British and French.³⁹ Similar to the attitude of the Ottoman Syrian and Iraqi provincial governments, who developed influential partnership relations with the various Shammār sheikhs in the late nineteenth century and mutualized the provincial and tribal interests, the French policy was usually to defend al-Hādī's actions, while the British advocated for the Iraqi tribes.⁴⁰ By 1928 the British and French officials were still discussing how to 'obviate the immediate necessity of their nationality',⁴¹ which resulted in the joint improvement of the security infrastructure in the Syrian and Iraqi sides of the desert and agreements regulating border crossing by the tribes.⁴² They also doggedly pursued tribal lootings on both sides of the border, which limited the manoeuvrability of actors such as al-Hādī,⁴³ although this took a long time.⁴⁴ Al-Hādī's attacks on the Iraqi territories had a heavy response from British troops,⁴⁵ which probably prevented al-Hādī from activities that would further anger the British and French – and he tended to confine himself to the privileges he had already obtained in Syria and Iraq to maintain his status in the newly emerging regional order.⁴⁶

During the naturalization of his tribespeople into Syrian nationality, the sheikh turned into an important translocal leader using their loyalty as a bargaining chip. In the meantime, the post of the Shammār sheikh transformed into an influential national and transnational institution in both countries, where the government appointed a new sheikh when the old one died and parliamentary membership of Iraq and Syria was automatically granted to the paramount sheikhs by default.⁴⁷ Thus, the border-making processes did not result in the complete nationalization or, in Michael Mann's terms, 'caging' of the tribal translocality.⁴⁸

*

Another important process that influenced the emergence of the modern Middle East, in which we can reveal an influential tribal agency, is the struggle between the Wahhabi supporter Ibn Saud (who

³⁷ T.N.A., CO 730/41, Baghdad, 6 Sept. 1923.

³⁸ T.N.A., CO 730/42, Baghdad, 27 Sept. 1923. For an account of the later attacks carried out by Dahhām's fellow tribespeople in and around Mosul, see C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/562, Dobb to high commissioner, Mosul, Wilson to Ripert, 15 Feb. 1928.

³⁹ See, e.g., C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/562, Aide-memoire, Saton to high commissioner, 22 Oct. 1927; 1SL/1/V/562, Délégué adjoint at Deir al-Zor to administrative advisor at Mosul, Deir al-Zor, 13 Jan. 1928.

⁴⁰ See, e.g., C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/562, Jouvenel to high commissioner in Baghdad, Beirut, 28 Apr. 1926, p. 26. For an analysis of the alliances between the various Shammār sheikhs and the neighbouring provinces, see Çiçek, *Negotiating Empire*, ch. 5; see also Dolbee, *Locusts of Power*, ch. 2.

⁴¹ C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/562, Dobb to high commissioner, 31 March 1928.

⁴² See, e.g., C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/562, Captain Terrier to High Commissioner Billotte, Abu Kemal, 20 Apr. 1933.

⁴³ Both mandates developed sophisticated techniques to prevent cross-border tax exaction by the Syrian Shammārs in Iraq, and vice versa. This constituted one of the most influential measures dissuading Dahhām from operating in Iraq. When he exacted duties from the Iraqi tribes, the intergovernmental mechanism was used to get it back. See C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/562, Dobb to high commissioner, 31 March 1928.

⁴⁴ See, e.g., C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/562, Saton to high commissioner, Beirut, 13 July 1925. See also the documents in the same file with the dossier title 'rezzou Chammar d'Adjil Yaouar' dated 1927 and 1928.

⁴⁵ For instance, al-Hādī lost forty-five of his men at one time in April 1926 (C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/562, newspaper clipping, 3 Apr. 1926). For another large-scale British operation against Dahhām, see al-Hamd, *Ashā'ir al-Raqqa wa al-Jazīra*, p. 184.

⁴⁶ When he lost the confidence of the mandates, Ajil al-Yāwīr's authority strengthened even among the Syrian Shammārs. In early 1927, for instance, al-Yāwīr could cross the border and offer his leadership to al-Hādī's fellow tribespeople (C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/562, 'Différend entre Chammar syriens et Adjil Yaouar', Deir al-Zor, 25 Jan. 1927).

⁴⁷ Oppenheim, *Die Bedouinen*, i. 151.

⁴⁸ See, e.g., British Library, EAP119/1/20/99, 'Raisu Ashā'ir al-Shammār', *Al-Qabas*, 6 Sept. 1934, p. 5 <<https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP119-1-20-99>> [accessed 12 May 2025]. For the term *caging*, see M. Mann, *The Sources of Social Power*, ii: *the Rise of Classes and Nation-States, 1760–1914* (Cambridge, 2013).

would become the first Saudi king) and the 'Anaza Bedouins. Ibn Saud appealed to the tribal customs and used the kinship ties to legitimize his claims of sovereignty over these societies as he was also an 'Anaza, although he was from the Masālikh section of the Hassa, a lesser tribe of the 'Anaza when compared to the Amārāt, Fid'an and Ruwalla, whose allegiance was demanded. Ibn Saud also alleged that these tribes had paid homage to his ancestor in the late eighteenth and early nineteenth century during the great Wahhabi revolt, which he claimed was still binding.⁴⁹ This is a particularly prominent chapter in a long history of attempts to mobilize the 'Anaza genealogy for political alliance building, which can be traced from the early nineteenth to the early twenty-first century. In this way, he would not only ensure the expansion of his influence in these new countries but also make these newly emerging states more dependent on him by controlling the desert territory between Iraq and the Mediterranean.⁵⁰ This Wahhabization project, however, posed an existential threat to both the social networks and economic relations of many translocal groups from the 'Anaza and Shammār tribes and the stability of the post-Ottoman mandate regimes.⁵¹ Therefore, the great majority of Syrian and Iraqi camel-herding Bedouin strove to restrict Wahhabi expansionism.

In this regard, the relations between Ibn Saud and the 'Anaza tribe Ruwalla, and their dispute over the strategic territory of al-Jawf, are highly representative to understand how Wahhabism threatened tribal autonomy and the regional order they wanted. Expanding sovereignty over al-Jawf, a region considered the gate for Syria and Palestine (*abwāb al-Shām wa Filastīn*),⁵² would provide a direct land connection between Syria and Arabia and enable Ibn Saud to spread Wahhabism among the tribal communities of the Shāmiya, the Jazīra and the Syrian Desert, and make large tribes of Syria and Transjordan dependent to him as they used al-Jawf and Wādī al-Sirhān to winter their animals, whose water sources were key to camel herders of Syria.⁵³ For Nūri al-Sha'lān (the Ruwalla sheikh), in addition to securing the winter pastures of his people, the region was an important place to remain a translocal regional actor between Iraq, Syria, Jordan and Arabia. Holding the possession of al-Jawf would enable him to negotiate with the British, the French, King Faisal, the Amir Abdullah and Ibn Saud, and establish a spatial resistance against being 'bordered'.⁵⁴

The region was also strategic for the British to provide security to the roads, the railways, and the oil pipeline that they planned to construct between Baghdad and the Mediterranean.⁵⁵ For the French, the control of the region by themselves – or by a tribal group under their sovereignty – meant both gaining an advantage over the British and annexing a strategic area in the north of Arabia, relatively close to Hijaz.

In this section, al-Sha'lān's diplomatic struggle to keep this region under his control in the first half of the 1920s is analysed. Although he failed to remove al-Jawf from the Saudi sovereignty, al-Sha'lān's anti-Wahhabi diplomacy influenced the ultimate status of the region enabling the Syrian and Iraqi tribes to use the region and maintain their translocal agency in the Middle East. His efforts against the expansion of Wahhabism probably influenced the outcome of border negotiations between Transjordan and Najd, which severed the land connection between Syria and Arabia.

From 1921 onwards, al-Sha'lān took advantage of every opportunity to gain control over the al-Jawf area. After the termination of the Rashidi dynasty by Ibn Saud and the de facto control of the

⁴⁹ For some details, see D. Chatty, *From Camel to Truck: the Bedouin in the Modern World* (Cambridge, 2013), pp. 57–60.

⁵⁰ For similar analyses, see C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/552, Tommy Martin to high commissioner, 10 Nov. 1923; see also C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/552, 'Rapport: Sur la situation des nomades et le fonctionnement du contrôle bédouin de l'état de Syrie pour l'année 1932, Annex 2', Damascus, 28 Feb. 1933.

⁵¹ T.N.A., CO 730/72, High commissioner to Foreign Affairs, Baghdad, 26 Jan. 1925.

⁵² Aminal-Rihāni, *Tārikh Najd al-Hadiith wa Mulhaqātuhā* (Beirut, 1928), p. 58.

⁵³ For a detailed study on the importance of al-Jawf for the Syrian and Iraqi tribes, see A. al-Bādī, *Al-Rihlatu al-Awrūbiyyūn fī Shimāli al-Jazīrati al-Arabiyyah: Mintqatu al-Jawf 1845-1922* (al-Jawf, 2011); on the Anizah-Shammār struggle over al-Jawf, see Max Freiherr von Oppenheim, *Die Bedouinen*, iii: *Die Bedouinenstämme in Nord- und Mittelarabien und im Irak* (Wiesbaden, 1952), pp. 37–44.

⁵⁴ Even in 1914 Nūri and his son Nāwawāf considered a British protectorate over al-Jawf like the one between the Amir of Kuwait and the British to maintain their control in the region against the Rashidis, who were generously supported by the Ottomans (al-Bādī, *Mintqatu al-Jawf*, p. 442).

⁵⁵ See, e.g., T.N.A., CO 730/23, Ibn Saud to high commissioner, Baghdad, 24 July 1922; and J. B. Philby, 'Jawf and the North Arabian desert', *Geographical Journal*, lxii (1923), 241–59. During the construction of the pipeline in 1936, the British were very sensitive of the need to keep the Anizah groups away so as not to slow down the project; see C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/552, Saury to general commander of Southern Syrian Troops, Palmyra, 18 Jan. 1936.

region by the Ruwalla, the French expressed their support for al-Sha'lān in the Jawf region.⁵⁶ However, when al-Sha'lān realized the low potential of the French to shelter them against Ibn Saud, the sheikh approached the Iraqi government and tried to persuade them to take control of al-Jawf, assuming that he would be protected against Wahhabism. In this regard, he first wrote a letter to Ali Sulaimān, the sheikh of the Dulaim tribe, stating that the entire Syrian desert, including al-Jawf, should be part of Iraq. He aimed to transmit the letter to the British and Iraqi authorities, which he achieved.⁵⁷ He then contacted King Faisal and made him a definite proposal, probably involving the capture of al-Jawf by the Ruwalla on behalf of the Iraqi government and annexing it to the mandate territory.⁵⁸

Although al-Sha'lān's endeavour before the Iraqi government did not bear fruit, the French mandate's negotiations with Ibn Saud on behalf of the Ruwalla through the mediation of the famous arms dealer Usaimī Pasha were productive as an agreement between al-Sha'lān and Ibn Saud was reached.⁵⁹ This initial agreement made Ibn Saud more ambitious about extending his influence to the 'Anaza tribes of Syria and Iraq. He sent letters to the tribal sheikhs in Syria proposing to meet in Kuwait within three months or they would be considered enemies,⁶⁰ which was followed by the Ruwalla's forced consent to Ibn Saud's vassalage in exchange for the recognition of their pasturage rights in the al-Jawf region. This agreement was to be recognized by both parties as the naturalization of the Ruwalla into Saudi nationality.⁶¹

However, Ibn Saud's hegemonic behaviour, coupled with the Ikhwān Wahhabi expansionism, was considered a serious threat by the Ruwalla and other tribes for their translocal agency and lifestyle. Al-Sha'lān was therefore aware that he needed to be backed by at least one major power to obtain permanent residence in the al-Jawf region and wanted the French troops to be stationed in al-Jawf. In this way, he would safely control the region under the French protection against Ibn Saud.⁶² However, the French did not accept this proposal, and his undertaking remained fruitless.⁶³ Deploying troops in a region as far away from Syria as al-Jawf and supplying them there presumably transcended the French military capacity in the region.⁶⁴

After the failure of his efforts with the French and the British mandates, al-Sha'lān approached King Abdullah and the Jordanian mandate officials.⁶⁵ John Philby, chief British representative in Transjordan, visited the al-Jawf region accompanied by several prominent sheikhs including Mithqal Pasha, the chief sheikh of the Bani Sakhr. Philby encouraged the local leaders to submit to Transjordan rather than Ibn Saud, with some success. Philby also negotiated with the local amirs regarding the project of a railway line from Baghdad to Haifa, passing through al-Jawf.⁶⁶ However, this visit alarmed Ibn Saud and he then occupied the region, compelling al-Sha'lān to retreat to Damascus with his tribe.⁶⁷ The sheikh of Ruwalla's simultaneous use of all the means at his disposal led to his loss of the region. In addition, the failure of the Philby's expedition into the region reduced the British enthusiasm to control the region as they realized the limits of their extended rule in al-Jawf region.⁶⁸

Although the British and French authorities were inclined to accept this Saudi *fait accompli*, al-Sha'lān was unwilling to let this matter drop. He sent a message to King Faisal through the high

⁵⁶ T.N.A., CO 730/23, 'Report on meeting with French representative at Albu Kamal', [?8 July 1922].

⁵⁷ T.N.A., CO 730/5, Baghdad, 1 Sept. 1921.

⁵⁸ T.N.A., CO 730/7, Baghdad, 11 Nov. 1921.

⁵⁹ T.N.A., CO 730/20, Damascus, 24 Feb. 1922.

⁶⁰ T.N.A., CO 730/20, Damascus, 21 Feb. 1922.

⁶¹ T.N.A., CO 730/23, 'Copy of "Treaty" between ourself and Nūri ibn Sha'lan', 12 Apr. 1922.

⁶² T.N.A., CO 730/23, Baghdad, 27 June 1922.

⁶³ T.N.A., CO 730/29, Damascus, 18 July 1922.

⁶⁴ The French army's military capacity was not sufficient even in 1925 for the interior of Syria. See, e.g., C.A.D.N., Cabinet politique, 1SL/1/V/549, Sarraïl, 9 March 1925.

⁶⁵ Abdullah used the argument of Arab unity to extend the Transjordanian territory to al-Jawf. Adding the region into the sovereignty of Jordan would provide land connection between Iraq and Transjordan and fulfil the first precondition of the two countries' unification. See al-Rihānī, *Tārīkh Najd*, p. 289.

⁶⁶ T.N.A., CO 730/23, Ibn Saud to high commissioner, Baghdad, 24 July 1922. For Philby's own description of the visit, see Philby, 'North Arabian desert'.

⁶⁷ Al-Rihānī, *Tārīkh Najd*, p. 288.

⁶⁸ Ibn Saud clearly stated in his letter to Usaimī Pasha that Nūri's cooperation with the British and Amir Abdullah compelled him to expel the Ruwalla from al-Jawf region; see T.N.A., CO 730/29, Ibn Saud to Usaimī, Damascus, 15 Sept. 1922.

commissioner asking for a meeting on the loss of al-Jawf. The Iraqi mandate officials responded that the government of Transjordan was interested in the matter and advised him to contact them.⁶⁹ When he was unable to resolve the matter through the latter and became aware of the influence of British Iraqi officials over Ibn Saud, al-Sha'lān visited Baghdad on 21 November 1923. The purpose of his visit was to get British support to recognize his rights in al-Jawf and the Qarayyat al-Milh area at the northern end of the Wādī Sirhān. The high commissioner told him that the ownership of al-Jawf region was disputed, as it had changed hands several times in the last hundred years between the amirs of Ruwalla and Hail, and whoever was more powerful controlled the area.⁷⁰ Thus, he left Baghdad empty-handed. Turning his face unwillingly again to Ibn Saud, al-Sha'lān repaired his relations with him in the subsequent years and the Ruwalla was allowed to use the pastures in al-Jawf during the winter season.⁷¹

However, Ibn Saud's efforts to convert the 'Anaza tribes of Syria and Iraq into Wahhabism continued. In early 1925 the king sent letters to Fahd Bey al-Hadhhdhāl of Iraq and Mijhim ibn Muhayd of Syria and other tribal leaders, inviting them to recognize him as their *imams* and emphasizing their common 'Anaza roots.⁷² Since Ibn Saud had used a similar excuse to expand in Yemen, where the 'Anaza tribes originated, the letter caused serious concern among the sheikhs, including that of the Ruwalla.⁷³ Al-Sha'lān used this as an opportunity to undermine the Saudi relations with the British and sent an envoy to King Faisal to ask him for advice. This news was sufficient to alarm the British, who warned that the spread of the Wahhabi influence would not be tolerated, considering that the Saudi domination of the Ruwalla would lead to a similar fate for the Amārāt tribe of Iraq and that this would pose a major threat to the new order they were trying to establish in the Middle East.⁷⁴ However, this diplomatic move also had consequences for the Ruwalla. Soon after that, the Ikhwān leaders sent a delegation to Fāwwāz, the grandson of al-Sha'lān, in the al-Jawf district, demanding his surrender.⁷⁵ This meant the end, at least for a while, of the Ruwalla's privilege to use the pastures in al-Jawf.

The ultimate status of the al-Jawf region was determined by the Haddā Agreement of 1925. Ibn Saud wanted to have a border with Syria and insisted on this during the negotiations. It was vital for the British, however, to have a land connection between Iraq, Jordan and Palestine, and to control the roads extending from Iraq and the Mediterranean. Both sides ultimately found a middle ground, agreeing that a seventy-mile corridor between Jordan and Iraq would become Jordanian territory. In return, almost all the Wādī Sirhān and al-Jawf were left to the Kingdom of Najd. Tribes such as Fid'an and Ruwalla were allowed to use this region without any restrictions. As Kenneth Williams points out, these agreements were *inevitably a mixture of the traditional law of the desert with international law*.⁷⁶ The relations between al-Sha'lān and the Saudis were also repaired, and the former was allowed to use the pastures in al-Jawf while maintaining his French-salaried-paramountcy in Syria. Ibn Saud's renouncement of the Wahhabi expansionism and elimination of the Ikhwān can be considered as the main reason for sustainable relations between the Ruwalla and the king. The reactions of such tribes as the Ruwalla to the extension of the Saudi sovereignty was among the reasons for such a radical policy shift from ideological expansionism to peaceful coexistence. Consequently, by 1930 the al-Sha'lān-Saudi relations in al-Jawf had improved so much that Ibn Mus'ad, the Saudi governor of the region, could organize a joint *ghazw* with some branches of the Ruwalla against the Transjordanian Huwaitāt tribe.⁷⁷ Relationships between the two sides were sealed by the marriage in 1935 of al-Sha'lān's granddaughter Nūf bint Nāwwāf to Ibn Saud, who was also a half-sister to Dahhām al-Fāyīz

⁶⁹ T.N.A., CO 730/26, 'Intelligence report', Baghdad, 15 Nov. 1922.

⁷⁰ T.N.A., CO 730/43, 'Intelligence report', Baghdad, 1 Dec. 1923.

⁷¹ See, e.g., T.N.A., CO 730/82, Baghdad, Feb. 1925.

⁷² T.N.A., CO 730/82, Baghdad, 12 Jan. 1925.

⁷³ Brit. Libr., EAP119/1/20/86, 'Al-Malik wa Mufawazāt bayna al-Ingiltere wa al-Yaman', *Al-Qabas*, 22 Aug. 1934, p. 1 <<https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP119-1-20-86>> [accessed 12 May 2025].

⁷⁴ T.N.A., CO 730/72, Baghdad, 16 Jan. 1925; CO 730/72, Baghdad, 22 Jan. 1925.

⁷⁵ T.N.A., CO 730/82, Baghdad, Feb. 1925.

⁷⁶ K. Williams, *Ibn Sa'ud: the Puritan King of Arabia* (London, 1933), pp. 182–4.

⁷⁷ C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/562, Chancellor to high commissioner, Jerusalem, 31 March 1930

of the Banī Sakhr Twāqa of Transjordan – which provided an opportunity to Ibn Saud to develop good relations with this influential tribe of the region.⁷⁸

*

An abundant number of ‘illicit arms’ spread throughout the Arab East and among the tribes during the first two decades of the twentieth century due to Saudi-Rashidi hostilities, the Arab Revolt and the Ottoman and British supply of arms to their tribal allies, which seriously threatened the regional security and state-building processes.⁷⁹ Rural security was particularly important for the British, as they planned to connect the mandates of Iraq, Jordan and Palestine by roads and railways and to lay an oil pipeline between Haifa and Baghdad. Therefore, they had to deal with this issue and strove hard to reduce arms smuggling to tolerable levels from the early years of the mandate. For the tribes, the issue was more complicated as they were both the customers of smugglers, crucial components of their networks, and, later, collaborators with the British, who played important roles in restricting arms smuggling. Armament composed an essential part of tribal life to protect themselves against other tribes and external threats, such as the Ikhwān Wahhabis. Thus, unarming them was an impossible undertaking. Even in 1935, highlighting the inefficiency of the disarmament operations in the desert, a French official described them as *une comédie*.⁸⁰ However, the solution to the issue required harmonized collaboration of the translocal tribal groups subordinated to the various states in the region. The arms trade could therefore be checked by recognizing the tribal rights of bearing arms.

Muhammad Pasha al-Usaimī, a native of Najd who had traded in Iraq during the Ottoman period, was at the centre of these gun-smuggling networks in the Arab East. After the British occupation, the Pasha had to live in Syria and was not allowed to enter Iraq as he was anti-British and on good terms with the Turks. It was feared that al-Usaimī would – in collaboration with the Turks – use his influence among tribes to incite them against the mandate. He skilfully benefitted from the new post-war conditions of the Middle East to maximize his profitable trade and played between the imperial, regional and local actors. His very good relations with the leading tribes of the region provided him a great advantage in the arms trade.⁸¹ Al-Usaimī also enjoyed good relations with other important actors in the region, such as Ibn Saud and al-Sha’lān, all of whom were crucial contacts for the distribution of arms. He was so close to Ibn Saud that the king had even appointed him as his representative in Damascus for a while.⁸²

The attitude of the French mandate officials also facilitated al-Usaimī’s business, with whom he developed friendly relations. His trans-border networks extending from Syria and Iraq to Najd and the Gulf – and good relations with the translocal nomads – were seen by the French as an opportunity to improve their relations with these regions and their actors.⁸³ Moreover, the French felt threatened by the British plans to unarm the desert as part of their policy of linking the British mandates in Jordan, Iraq and Palestine. The French policymakers considered the Haifa-Baghdad railway project as part of a strategy to contain their mandate territories from the east and south.⁸⁴ Consequently, in the early 1920s, as the French did not see arms smuggling as a major problem, Damascus became central for the distribution of arms throughout the rural areas of the Arab East.⁸⁵

Although al-Usaimī was at the centre of the arms trade, many individuals and groups were incorporated into these networks in one way or another – as customers or entrepreneurs. Al-Sha’lān

⁷⁸ ‘Nūf bint Nāwaf bin Nūrī’, *Geneanet* <<https://gw.geneanet.org/frebault?lang=en&pz=henri&nz=frebault&m=P&v=nuf+bint+nawaf+bin+nuri>> [accessed 10 Jan. 2023].

⁷⁹ For an article on the Ottoman history of gun smuggling, see R. H. Öztan, ‘Tools of revolution: global military surplus, arms dealers and smugglers in the late Ottoman Balkans, 1878–1908’, *Past & Present*, cccxxvii (2017), 167–95; on the Rashidi-Saudi conflict, see M. T. Çiçek, ‘The tribal partners of empire in Arabia: the Ottomans and the Rashidis of Najd, 1880–1918’, *New Perspectives on Turkey*, lvi (2017), 105–30; on the Arab Revolt, see E. Rogan, *The Fall of the Ottomans* (London, 2015), ch. 11; on arms smuggling and trade in Arabia, see Pétriat, *Last Caravan*, pp. 188–92.

⁸⁰ They kept their old and unused weapons at hand to deliver to the army when they were requested (C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/552, ‘Bulletin hebdomadaire d’information no 19 – période du 15 au 23 mai 1935’, 27 May 1935).

⁸¹ T.N.A., CO 732/6, Damascus, 10 May 1922.

⁸² T.N.A., CO 730/21, ‘Intelligence report’, Baghdad, 15 Apr. 1922; CO 730/21, Ibn Saud to Cox, Baghdad, 19 Apr. 1922.

⁸³ T.N.A., CO 732/1, Damascus, 5 Apr. 1921.

⁸⁴ T.N.A., CO 730/19, Baghdad, 6 Jan. 1922.

⁸⁵ T.N.A., CO 730/9, Damascus, 2 May 1921.

of the Ruwalla and his son Nāwḥāf took important roles in the arms traffic organized by al-Usaimī.⁸⁶ They wanted to sell their weapons to the tribes of the Euphrates basin, for which the most practical way was to use al-Usaimī's contacts.⁸⁷ The British believed that Ottoman weapons in Hama, Aleppo and Homs were being circulated regionally through the Ruwalla tribe.⁸⁸ As the tribes of the Euphrates were disarmed by the British after the 1920 Revolt of Iraq, supplying them with weapons was a lucrative business. Ibn Saud was another important customer of al-Usaimī, to whom he supplied a large number of weapons needed for the operations of the Ikhwān Wahhābis.⁸⁹

Arms trafficking in the Arab East also intermingled regional and global networks in which many of the region's most influential leaders were involved. A route extending from the Red Sea through Syria, Hail and Najd to the Persian Gulf and Kuwait was used for arm smuggling. Since the Ottoman times, Hail had been an important centre for arms coming from the Red Sea and Medina and from the Persian Gulf via Kuwait to Mesopotamia.⁹⁰ In addition, there were many Ottoman weapons and those of the Sharif Hussein's troops in the Syrian cities left over from the First World War and the Faisal's kingship era, which were gradually shipped eastwards by the tribes.⁹¹ As the French mandate officials wanted to be rid of these weapons, they encouraged the trade of trans-border arms towards Iraq, Arabia and the Gulf, which would disarm the French mandate territories in Syria and Lebanon.⁹² Furthermore, the Syrian mandate's ban on arms ownership by tribal groups other than nomads forced sedentary and semi-sedentary tribes to sell their weapons to nomads, which released them into circulation among the tribes of Iraq, Jordan and Najd.⁹³

The global networks of anti-colonialism constituted another source for the Middle Eastern suppliers. After the First World War Italy established a centre for the anti-British anti-colonial struggle, the League of Oppressed Nations (League of Fiume). To support all the oppressed nationalities in their struggle for political dignity and recognition,⁹⁴ they facilitated the supply of arms to the British imperial territories. These weapons were procured in Germany, loaded onto ships in Italy and transported to the Red Sea ports, from where they were distributed through an extensive network reaching the Arab East and Anatolia. The tribal migration routes and their translocal trade connections were integrated into these global gunrunning networks,⁹⁵ making it impossible for the British to solve the problem without the help of the major tribal groups. The smuggling was so clandestine that even in January 1922 the British had limited knowledge of the movements of the weapons being traded.⁹⁶ A major reason for this was the security problem in the desert, which compelled the authorities to allow caravans to carry one weapon per camel, and this was often 'abused' by distributing weapons in small quantities between different caravans.⁹⁷ For example, to avoid being caught for arms smuggling, a caravan of 100 camels travelling to Iraq would take 100 weapons, sell 80 of them and return with the remaining 20.⁹⁸

Some distant villages were used as bases for trans-border regional arms trafficking. The border village of Qubaishah, located in the Iraqi territory, had long been a place where arms coming from Syria were distributed. Several villagers engaged in this business had been identified by the British and proven guilty.⁹⁹ Two caravans that arrived at Qubaishah in February 1921 demonstrate the extent of the local and regional networks, the variety of the actors involved in the arms trade and their

⁸⁶ T.N.A., CO 730/9, Damascus, 30 Apr. 1921.

⁸⁷ T.N.A., CO 730/9, Damascus, 30 Apr. 1921.

⁸⁸ T.N.A., CO 730/9, Damascus, 5 May 1921.

⁸⁹ T.N.A., CO 730/7, Fortnightly report, Baghdad, 1–15 Oct. 1921.

⁹⁰ T.N.A., CO 730/4, Baghdad, 5 Aug. 1921.

⁹¹ T.N.A., CO 730/9, Damascus, 5 May 1921.

⁹² T.N.A., CO 730/4, Baghdad, 22 July 1921.

⁹³ T.N.A., CO 730/9, Damascus, 30 Apr. 1921.

⁹⁴ The league did not have any direct link to the Bedouin. They supplied arms to the Middle East simply to destabilize British imperialism. As the Bedouin always needed weapons in their struggle with the rival tribes and to feel secure against external attacks, including those by the various governments in the region, they were the potential customers of the illicit arms supplied to the Middle East by the league, and these weapons frequently ended up in the tribal encampments. For more detail on the league and its activities, see M. A. Ledeen, *D'Annunzio: the First Duce, the League of Fiume* (Piscataway, N.J., 2002).

⁹⁵ T.N.A., CO 730/9, Beirut to Baghdad, 'Syria: political', 1 March 1921; CO 732/4, [?Egypt], 11 Apr. 1921.

⁹⁶ T.N.A., CO 730/19, Baghdad, 6 Jan. 1922.

⁹⁷ T.N.A., CO 730/19, Baghdad, 6 Jan. 1922.

⁹⁸ T.N.A., CO 732/6, Damascus, 4 Feb. 1922.

⁹⁹ T.N.A., CO 730/7, Baghdad, 11 Nov. 1921.

political-ideological diversity: they belonged to the Baghdadi merchant Ibrāhīm Mumeyr, the Damascene Ibrāhīm Dalūl and a Najdi merchant, who were accompanied by eleven former officers of Sharif Hussein's army – presumably former unemployed Ottoman officers. The caravans reportedly carried 400 guns and large quantities of ammunition.¹⁰⁰

The translocal networks of the nomads enabled the quick transfer of guns from one region to another, which made their detection and restriction very difficult. When arms were needed in a certain region, they could be quickly transported by means of the translocal networks of the nomads. As the motivation for high commercial profit constituted the basic reason behind this speed, it is difficult to talk about an anti-colonial tribal collaboration or any sort of nationalist solidarity. Due to the very high prices, for instance, the 'Unayzā tribe of the Qasim had sold most of their weapons to gun smugglers to be marketed among the Iraqi tribes during the great revolt of 1920. When they again needed weapons for personal use, they could purchase them easily using the smuggling networks.¹⁰¹

Due to the complexity of the networks used and the diversity of actors involved, the arms trade constituted an intricate issue for the British to resolve without the tribal collaboration and mutual goodwill on all sides. The British used almost all their influence over the French and tribal actors to prevent arms trade. Consequently, by March 1923 the illicit arms trade had declined to negligible levels. The recognition of the arms ownership rights of the nomadic tribes by the British and French mandates and allowing them to bear arms outside the sedentary areas constituted an important reason for the tribal willingness to co-operate for the prevention of illicit arms trafficking in the region.¹⁰² The biggest partner of the mandate rule in this business was Fahd Bey ibn Hadhdhāl, the sheikh of the Amārāt tribe, who seized many illicit weapons traded by al-Usaimī. This situation, however, created a rift between Ibn Saud and Ibn Hadhdhāl, as the former had procured arms by al-Usaimī and his commercial partners.¹⁰³ The British had to intervene and explain to Ibn Saud that it was they who did not allow the passage of weapons through Iraqi territory and that Ibn Hadhdhāl had been authorized by them to forestall arms trafficking.¹⁰⁴ Ibn Saud then made great efforts to block the smuggling of arms and acquired considerable achievements. Additionally, the French introduced strict control in the rural areas of Syria, which significantly reduced the operational skills of such actors as al-Usaimī and the Ruwāla.¹⁰⁵

The Sykes-Picot Agreement is often considered as the sole factor determining the border-drawing processes in the post-Ottoman Middle East. Although the decisions of Western imperialists in the drawing of these borders can never be underestimated and the Sykes-Picot vision was put into practice, at least in its basic outline, this state-centric and overgeneralizing perspective does not indicate how translocal actors like the tribes influenced the border-making processes in the region. The tribal communities struggled to protect their translocal character, which remarkably influenced the 'borderization' processes of the Arab East. As successfully indicated by Wilkinson, the three notions of territory: tribal, Islamic and international, contested – and finally conciliated – in the making of the boundaries in the Middle East, which was represented by the Bedouin, Saudi Arabia and the mandatory powers. Tribal notion was expressed in terms of securing access to grazing areas and rain-fed farming lands while Ibn Saud demanded *zakāt* (religious tax) to confirm the loyalty of his followers and the mandatory states tried to enforce the international law.¹⁰⁶ Consequently, while the tribes ultimately accepted the main principles of the international boundary notion and respected Ibn Saud's authority, the tribal notion of territory was in response largely recognized by the other sides of the negotiations and trans-border grazing privileges had to be guaranteed by treaties delimiting

¹⁰⁰ T.N.A., CO 730/9, Beirut to Baghdad, 'Syria: political', 1 March 1921.

¹⁰¹ T.N.A., CO 730/9, Damascus, 8 July 1921.

¹⁰² C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/552, 'Arrete no 323 relatif à la réglementation du mouvement de transhumance des tribus bedouines au cours de l'été 1922', Damascus, 27 Jan. 1922.

¹⁰³ T.N.A., CO 730/7, Baghdad, 10 July 1921.

¹⁰⁴ T.N.A., CO 730/7, Baghdad, 23 Sept. 1921.

¹⁰⁵ T.N.A., CO 730/57, 'Report on Iraq administration', Baghdad, Apr. 1922–March 1923; CO 730/43, 'Intelligence report', Baghdad, 1 Dec. 1923. For a summary of French security measures in rural Syria, see C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/552, 'Ordre generale no 296', Beirut, 22 Feb. 1925; the subsequent documents in the same file also concern the French security situation in the desert in the first half of the 1920s.

¹⁰⁶ J. C. Wilkinson, 'Nomadic territory as a factor in defining Arabia's boundaries', in Mundy and Musallam, *Transformation of Nomadic Society*, pp. 44–62.

the borders between the states in the region, from which a historical experience of translocalization emerged.

*

Immediately after his accession to the throne of Iraq, Faisal began to pursue the policy of expanding his sphere of influence among the tribes of Syria, where he was already popular. The king had ruled Syria between 1918–20 and the former Ottoman officers employed in his administration had expanded his influence among the Bedouin tribes in the Syria-Iraq borderland area.¹⁰⁷ Therefore, adopting a policy of territory synthesizing the tribal and the Islamic notions, the king argued that the tribes living in the Syrian-Iraqi border area should be given the right to choose which state they would be subject to, presumably because he thought he could convince the Syrian tribes to accept his authority. In this regard, Faisal advocated that the Khabur River should be the natural border separating the two countries.¹⁰⁸ The Iraqi government maintained this position for a while, offering to acquire the whole of Jabal Sinjar in exchange for the Khabur valley to ensure the integrity of the tribal areas. Otherwise, in Faisal's viewpoint, the division of the border would have occurred in an *unnatural* way.¹⁰⁹

After several failed attempts to construct 'unnatural' borders between the two countries in line with the international boundary-making procedures, the British and French mandate officials came to the conclusion that the Syrian-Iraqi border could be given its final shape if the disputes between the borderland tribes were settled. The border would then fulfil its legal purpose of separating the two countries from each other. The officials of the border committee were convinced that the determination of the tribal borders, such as those between Aqaidât and Dulaim, and the solution of the tribal disputes like the Shammâr-Aqaidât and Amârât-Aqaidât were prerequisites for the demarcation of the Syrian-Iraqi national border.¹¹⁰ The ongoing blood feud and trans-border land disputes between these tribes led to major incidents that seriously disrupted the borderland peace of both countries and made the construction of a functioning border impossible. Therefore, a commission was set up in early 1923 to delimit the Dulaim-Aqaidât tribal boundary and, in April 1923, a meeting was held solely to determine the areas inhabited by these two tribes.¹¹¹

Once the mandate governments realized that the other part of the problem was their lack of understanding regarding the components of the tribal trans-border lifestyles, they sought to find more 'innovative' solutions to build an order in which the tribal mobility occupied a place. In this sense, a key initiative was the establishment of a permanent interstate, intertribal court (*tribunal mixte*) to hear trans-border cases. It was established in September 1924 and consisted of two Syrian and two Iraqi tribal representatives, and two British, French, Iraqi and Syrian officials.¹¹² As a final step to tranquilize the Iraqi-Syrian borderland, the Dulaim and Aqaidât tribes were persuaded to sign a peace ending all blood feuds and resolving all the disputes between them.¹¹³ However, the Dulaim-Aqaidât conflict could not be eliminated as they continued to attacking each other. By early 1930 the two tribes still remained at the heart of the Syrian-Iraqi border disputes and both empires maintained their efforts for 'the settlement of the problems between the Dulaim and Aqaidât tribes with a view to establishing a permanent state of peace between them.'¹¹⁴

¹⁰⁷ For further detail, see Barr, *Line in the Sand*, ch. 8.

¹⁰⁸ T.N.A., CO 730/19, Baghdad, 10 Feb. 1922. In a later phase, the French would use the Aqaidât tribe to expand his territorial claims into the Iraqi territory. See, e.g., C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/558, 'Rapport du Colonel Andrea, président de la delegation syrienne a la Conference de Deir-*ez-Zor*, Deir al-Zor, 30 July 1923.

¹⁰⁹ T.N.A., CO 730/38, Baghdad, 31 Jan. 1923.

¹¹⁰ See, e.g., C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/558, Billotte to high commissioner, Aleppo, [?] April 1923, 30 July 1923; T.N.A., CO730/75, Baghdad, 9 Apr. 1923.

¹¹¹ T.N.A., CO 730/75, Baghdad, 12 Apr. 1923. On an agreement reached between these two tribes through negotiations arranged by French and British officials, see C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/558, 'Acte d'engagement des Chefs Delims, Djaghaiifa, Ogueidats et Beggaras', Deir al-Zor, 28 July 1923.

¹¹² T.N.A., CO 730/76, Baghdad, 28 May 1925. For some of the cases heard in the court, see C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/562, 'Procès-verbal de la reunion du Tribunal Mixte en sa séance du 28 Aout 1930 a Deraa', Der'a, 28 Aug. 1930.

¹¹³ T.N.A., CO 730/61, 'Intelligence report', Baghdad, 6 Sept. 1924.

¹¹⁴ C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/562, Captain Terrier to High Commissioner Billotte, Abu Kemal, 20 Apr. 1933.

The mandate governments also made several ingenious arrangements in the Syrian-Iraqi border delimitation agreement that would make it more functional and strengthen the authority of the states, but at the same time allow the tribes to maintain their mobile existence. In this regard, the Syrian and Iraqi tribes could freely move from one country to another for the seasonal grazing needs of their animals. Noteworthy reports can be found in newspapers on the seasonal trans-border migration of tribes such as the Ruwala and Seb'a and their return at the end of the grazing season.¹¹⁵ Another issue regulated in the border agreement was the political relations between the tribes and neighbouring countries when they crossed the border. In this regard, when a tribe migrated to the bordering state, the politicians of the host country were not to communicate with their sheikhs and not to encourage them to change their nationality. This clause was in all likelihood added at the request of the French, as they were disturbed by the activities of the Syrian tribes to improve their relations with the British and King Faisal.¹¹⁶ If a tribe rebelled against their state and took refuge in the bordering state, the latter would co-operate to keep the tribes away from the border area as much as possible and disarm them. The frequent escape of the tribal groups into Iraq and Transjordan during the Great Syrian Revolt of 1925 constituted a reason for the inclusion of this article.¹¹⁷

The border delimitation agreement also contained sophisticated rules regulating the treatment of conflicts among the tribes of Syria and Iraq and distributing responsibility between the states and tribes. In this regard, if a Syrian tribe attacked an Iraqi tribe and vice versa, the guilty sheikh and his state would be responsible for the return of the looted property, wherever the attack took place. However, the two governments were to co-operate in identifying the criminals and conducting the investigation process. Secondly, when a tribe entered the territory of a neighbouring state, they would be subject to the law and authority of that government. In the case of plundering, that state would have the right to take back the looted property by force and return them to their original owners. If this could not be possible, their national state would be responsible for the return of the goods. Furthermore, both states were to take measures to prevent the border from being used as a security shield to attack and plunder the tribes of the neighbouring state. In the case of disputes between sedentary people and tribes, the national courts of the latter's country would be responsible for resolving the problem. This rule was to apply to all cases from 1921 onwards.¹¹⁸ These were very similar to the procedures put into practice by the Ottoman government to co-ordinate its Syrian and Iraqi provinces to deal with the tribal affairs.

The tribal obstacles to the functionalization of the Syrian-Iraqi border were thus resolved towards the end of the 1920s, with the recognition of their rights of cross-border migration.¹¹⁹ In addition to the above-detailed regulations, a sophisticated intergovernmental mechanism was established to address trans-border intertribal issues, which led to a more peaceful situation in the Syrian-Iraqi borderland. Officials from both sides occasionally settled the accumulated trans-border disputes of tribes. For example, in May 1930 animals raided by the Ruwala of Syria from the Amārāt of Iraq were collected and returned to their original owners by the French desert police of the Rutbah.¹²⁰ Similarly, on 25 May 1934 a delegation headed by al-Ayyubi Bey, a senior Syrian official, including the governor of Deir al-Zor and the four French mandate officials travelled to Baghdad to sort out the trans-border

¹¹⁵ See Brit. Libr., EAP119/1/12/81, 'Rujū' al-*Ashā'ir* al-Sūriyā, al-Jāmi'ah al-Islāmiyah, 21 May 1933, p. 2 <<https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP119-1-12-81>> [accessed 12 May 2025].

¹¹⁶ According to a later report summarizing the tribal history under the French mandate, some important Syrian tribes settled in Iraq due to the land and watering advantages provided by the impact of the Iraqi government (C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/552, 'Notes A/S. des bedouins en Syrie', Damascus, 31 May 1940).

¹¹⁷ M. Al-Rayyis, *Al-Kitāb al-Zahabi li al-Thawrat al-Wataniyya fi al-Mashriq al-Arabi: Al-Thawratu al-Sūriyā al-Qubrā* (Beirut, 1969), pp. 210–14; and M. S. Al-Ās, *Safha min al-Ayyāmu al-Hamrā: Mudhakkirāt al-Qāid Sa'id al-Ās* (Beirut, 1929), p. 164.

¹¹⁸ T.N.A., CO 730/93, Baghdad, 3 May 1926; these regulations could be possible after long-lasting negotiations between officials and tribes in Syria and Iraq. For an example from 1923, see C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/558, 'Rapport du Colonel Andrea, president de la delegation syrienne a la Conference de Deir-*ez-Zor*', Deir al-Zor, 30 July 1923.

¹¹⁹ A French report summarizing the tribal events of 1930 notes that 'the peace was undoubtedly perfect' ('la paix a été parfaite sans doute'; C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/552, 'Exposé de la situation de tribus nomades en 1930', Beirut, 6 Jan. 1930).

¹²⁰ C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/562, Directeur du service des renseignements du Levant to high commissioner, 'Agissements anglais envers les tribus syriennes', Beirut, 6 May 1930. A similar process took place in early 1935 between the French mandate, the Ruwala and the Amārāt (C.A.D.N., 1SL/1/V/562, D. de Martel to high commissioner, 'Noury Chaalan', Beirut, 25 Feb. 1935).

disputes between the tribes of Syria and Iraq.¹²¹ The translocal character of tribal communities could thus be protected against the limitations imposed by nationalization.¹²²

*

It can be confidently argued that tribal agency played as decisive a role in the demarcation of the Saudi-Iraqi border as international law. The tribal loyalties determined sovereignty in many disputed areas. From the outset of border negotiations, Ibn Saud argued that tribal grazing areas should be used as a reference point for determining sovereignty over the disputed areas. In his viewpoint, the tribes were to decide which state they would pledge allegiance to. However, as will be analysed later, he did not tend to leave the decision to the tribes themselves and used the Ikhwān terror to ‘persuade’ the various tribal groups in Iraq to accept Saudi nationality. While the British initially found Ibn Saud’s idea of tribal boundaries ‘childish’,¹²³ in time they too came to realize that tribes and the territories they controlled had to be considered during border negotiations.¹²⁴

Ibn Saud was ambitious to extend his sovereignty, sooner or later, northwards into the Iraqi territory and collect *zakāt* from the major tribes there. In addition, important Saudi tribes, such as the Mutayr, who constituted the backbone of the Ikhwān, were very motivated to move towards the Euphrates basin to acquire better grazing areas. These made the major ‘Anaza groups in Iraq anxious about the Wahhabi expansionism. However, the British assured Fahd Bey ibn Hadhdhāl that he would also be available to represent the interests of the Amārāt at a meeting between Faisal and Ibn Saud.¹²⁵ Thus, the mandate administration, the Iraqi and Najdi governments and the tribal representatives became the parties to a border agreement. They agreed that tribal grazing areas and water wells should be the main parameters for demarcating the Najd-Iraq border, although the British authorities initially favoured the restriction of tribal cross-border movement.¹²⁶ However, Ibn Saud wanted to control all the desert zone between Iraq and Arabia, arguing that it would be very difficult to ensure peace if the power was divided between the two states in the desert.¹²⁷

With the Muhammara Agreement of 5 May 1922 – the first serious attempt to delimit the border between the two states – the parties determined well-known tribal boundaries in the desert. In addition, Ibn Saud recognized for the first time that the Muntafiq, Dhafir and Amārāt tribes were Iraqi subjects. As these tribes considered Wahhabism as an existential threat, it was they who requested to remain in Iraqi nationality. The Shammār refugees, who had been residents of Jabal Shammār and followers of Ibn Rashid before the termination of the Rashidi Amirate but had subsequently defected to Iraq, were recognized as citizens of the Kingdom of Najd. It was agreed that the tribes using pastures across the border would have to pay grazing tax. The agreement would be void if one of the signatories disagreed with the British, which meant that Ibn Saud could have expanded his territory towards Iraq when the mandate ended. A ‘rhomboid-like’ area on the south-eastern edge of Iraq was declared a neutral zone, demilitarized, and allocated for the communal use of the Iraqi and Najdi tribes.¹²⁸ In December 1922 the Iraqi government additionally accepted the right of the Najd tribes to water their animals on the Iraqi side, as that was where most of the wells were.¹²⁹

The Kuwait Conference of 1923 was the second major meeting organized to negotiate the Saudi-Iraqi border.¹³⁰ The Iraqi delegation that left Baghdad for Kuwait on December 4 to attend this conference

¹²¹ Brit. Libr., EAP119/1/12/228, ‘Mashākilu al-Hudūd’, *al-Jāmi‘ah al-Islāmiyah*, 1 June 1934, p. 3 <<https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP119-1-12-228>> [accessed 12 May 2025].

¹²² This situation, however, caused the maintenance of the activities of both states to increase their influence among the trans-border tribal communities, which would strengthen their cross-border leverage. See, e.g., C.A.D.N., ISL/1/V/552, ‘Exposé de la situation de tribus nomades en 1930’, Beirut, 6 Jan. 1930.

¹²³ High Commissioner Percy Cox had tried to determine the border by drawing a line on the map at the 1922 Ukayr Conference (Kostiner, ‘Transforming dualities’, p. 230).

¹²⁴ Williams, *Ibn Sa‘ud*, pp. 148–9.

¹²⁵ T.N.A., CO 730/8, Baghdad, 15 Dec. 1921.

¹²⁶ T.N.A., CO 730/21, High commissioner to Ibn Saud, Baghdad, 3 Apr. 1922.

¹²⁷ T.N.A., CO 730/21, Ibn Saud to Cox, Baghdad, 1 Apr. 1922.

¹²⁸ Williams, *Ibn Sa‘ud*, pp. 146–9.

¹²⁹ T.N.A., CO 730/26, Protocol 1: Najd & Iraq Boundary, 2 Dec. 1922.

¹³⁰ For a contemporaneous report on the details of the conference, see ‘Mu’tamar al-Kuwayt’, *Lisan al-Hal*, 15 Sept. 1925.

also included 'Ajil al-Yāwir, the paramount sheikh of the Shammār tribe.¹³¹ Although the conference was interrupted due to disagreements between the delegations¹³², a number of key decisions regarding the tribes were taken, very similar to the decisions agreed between the French and British on Syrian-Iraqi tribal relations.¹³³ Subsequently, Ibn Saud and Gilbert Clayton signed the Bahrā Agreement on 2 November 1925, delimiting the Iraqi-Najd border and establishing a tribal regime between the British mandates and Najd. According to the clauses of the agreement, tribes and their sheikhs were not to be contacted by neighbouring governments other than their national government. The troops of both countries were not to cross the border to pursue tribal groups. As for the cross-border raids, the tribal community that did the looting would be penalized, and their sheikh would be held responsible for the return. Ibn Saud accepted the establishment of an interstate tribal court authorized to deal with the issue of the *ghazw* and casualties with equal representation from Iraq and Najd and chaired by a neutral person, to which he had previously objected. It was also agreed that deterrent measures should be taken against the cross-border migration of nomads between Iraqi and Najd regions.¹³⁴ Consequently, by the pressure of the British, too, both sides agreed that tribes should be less mobile.

It is difficult, however, to argue that the Bahrā Agreement resolved the trans-border tribal issues. The ongoing Ikhwān terror, locust infestations and successive drought seasons made it impossible to prevent the tribes of each side from organizing cross-border *ghazws*. To put an end to this, the Iraqi side decided in the autumn of 1927 to set up several police posts on the Iraq-Najd frontier, equipped with radios to immediately report any violation to the Royal Air Force and the Iraqi Camel Corps. This move, however, breached the mutual agreement on the demilitarization of watering areas in the desert in the 1922 Uqayr Agreement and undermined the Saudi intentions to gradually Wahhabize the Iraqi tribes. The government of Riyadh, concerned about the complete colonization of the desert by the British, strongly objected to this militarization action on the grounds that it abolished the ancient desert custom of migrating wherever there was water and pasture. Bedouins also defended this position, as the deployment of the desert would restrict their freedom. When the Iraqi government refused to remove these military posts, the Wahhabi-Ikhwān forces fiercely attacked and destroyed them, inflicting heavy casualties on the surrounding tribes.¹³⁵

Mutual incursions and tribal attacks on the Iraqi-Saudi border continued until the Ikhwān Wahhabi forces rebelled against Ibn Saud in 1927 and were completely disbanded, which signified the end of the Wahhabi expansionism and the initiation of a peaceful relationship between the 'Anaza of Iraq and the Kingdom of Najd. In addition, the establishment of the Iraqi Camel Corps and building up an intelligence network among the camel herding Bedouin tribes of Iraq by Glubb Pasha constituted another factor in turning the tide in the Saudi-Iraqi frontier.¹³⁶ Thereafter, intertribal conflicts between Iraq and Arabia diminished considerably, while the cross-border migration of tribes continued. By the mid 1930s the Iraqi and Najdi tribes could peacefully share grazing lands, and the latter could easily come to Iraq to trade and sell their products.¹³⁷ In 1935 the officials of both countries even planned a conference between themselves and the tribal representatives of both countries to resolve trans-border issues.¹³⁸ In conclusion, it can be argued that tribal interests, agency and lifestyle had a significant impact on the demarcation of the Saudi-Iraqi border.

*

The emergence of the mandatory empires in the Arab East and the drawing of borders between Syria, Iraq, Jordan and Saudi Arabia in many ways redefined the order of things in the region. It might be

¹³¹ T.N.A., CO 730/44, Baghdad, 15 Dec. 1923.

¹³² T.N.A., CO 730/58, Baghdad, 17 Apr. 1924.

¹³³ T.N.A., CO 730/73, Baghdad, 18 March 1925.

¹³⁴ T.N.A., CO 730/80, Baghdad, 12 Nov. 1925. For a study on the political activities of Gilbert Clayton in the formative years of the post-Ottoman Middle East, see T. Paris, *In Defence of Britain's Middle Eastern Empire: a Life of Sir Gilbert Clayton* (Liverpool, 2015).

¹³⁵ Williams, *Ibn Sa'ud*, pp. 215–18.

¹³⁶ For a detailed description of Glubb's activities, see Glubb, *War in the Desert*, chs. 18–19.

¹³⁷ Brit. Libr., EAP119/1/12/377, 'Al-Ashā'ir al-Najdiyya wa al-Iraqiyya, *al-Jāmi'ah al-Islāmiyyah*, 5 Feb. 1935, p. 3 <<https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP119-1-12-377>> [accessed 12 May 2025]; and 'Al-Taqarrub bayna al-Mamlakat al-Sa'ūdiyya wa al-Iraq' (see n. 73), p. 6.

¹³⁸ Brit. Libr., EAP119/1/12/436, 'Mu'tamar al-Ashā'ir al-Janūbiyya, *al-Jāmi'ah al-Islāmiyyah*, 15 July 1935, p. 4 <<https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP119-1-12-436>> [accessed 12 May 2025].

misleading, however, to assume that the French and British empires set all the rules, determined everything and disregarded the concerns of the local actors during the sociopolitical formation of the region in the 1920s. The new translocal/trans-border order of the rural areas presented a contrast to the Western plans for the partition of the Middle East. As this study has demonstrated, the tribal interests and concerns had a significant impact on imperial decisions, compelling the French and British to retreat from many of their original plans. In this regard, although a well-defined notion citizenship restricting the movement of their adherents within the national boundaries would be preferable to the Western imperialists, the question of tribal nationality could only be solved by making significant cross-border concessions to the tribal groups that maintained their mobile translocal existence. Similarly, the present article has demonstrated the contribution of tribal agency to the containment of the Wahhabi expansionism, which posed a major threat to the emerging regional order. The Ruwala struggle against the Saudi domination of the strategic al-Jawf region between Iraq, Jordan, Syria and Arabia made an impact on the severing of the land link between Syria and Arabia by handing over a seventy-mile strip of land between Iraq and Jordan to the British mandate and reduced the Wahhabis' ability to exert influence among the Syrian and Iraqi tribal communities. The tribal agency also played a remarkable part in establishing a sustainable regional order by blocking arms-smuggling networks in the Arab East. However, they largely protected their right to bear arms in non-sedentary desert areas. Finally, the tribal groups became active participants in the border demarcation processes, both in obtaining significant exemptions from the border regulations and in determining the regions divided by the border line. It is not an exaggeration to conclude that the boundaries could only be functional by recognizing the tribes' rights to easily cross them.